

A SIDDHA MEDICINE *MARUNTHU* DESCRIBED IN THE *PITHA KARMA SANTHI* CONTEXT AND ITS POTENTIAL ROLE IN PSYCHIATRIC DISORDERS: A NARRATIVE REVIEW

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ABSTRACT

Psychiatric disorders contribute significantly to the global burden of disease and often require long-term care and follow-up. In this regard, the Siddha system of medicine provides a comprehensive approach to their management, incorporating both internal medicines and external therapies, as described in classical texts. The present review highlights a Siddha medicinal formulation *Marunthu* described in the context of *Pitha Karmam* in *Naarpathen Siddharkal Periya Gnana Kovai*. It evaluates its relevance to psychiatric conditions through a comprehensive analysis of classical Siddha texts, peer-reviewed literature, and electronic databases. The review summarizes the traditional indications, pharmacological activities of the constituent herbs, and their possible mechanisms of action. The findings suggest that *Marunthu* from *Pitha Karmam* context may have potential benefits in the management of psychiatric disorders through its neuroprotective, antioxidant, and

therapeutic effects in psychiatric disorders. However, systematic clinical studies and well-designed trials are required to validate its safety and efficacy. Integrating traditional

knowledge with contemporary research may help expand therapeutic options for psychiatric care. Furthermore, the standardization of the formulation, along with the elucidation of molecular mechanisms, pharmacokinetics, and long-term safety profiles, will facilitate the wider acceptance and integration of Siddha formulations into mainstream psychiatric practice.

KEYWORDS: Siddha Psychiatry, Zingiber officinale, Donkey milk, Non-Centrifugal Cane Sugar, Mental health.

INTRODUCTION

Mental health disorders affect over one billion individuals globally, according to the World Health Organization (WHO), with anxiety and depression accounting for a significant proportion of the associated human and economic burden. These conditions span all age groups and socioeconomic backgrounds and are among the leading causes of long-term disability worldwide and lead to increased health-care costs and substantial global economic losses.^[1]

The Siddha system of medicine provides a holistic framework for the understanding and management of mental health disorders. It explains psychiatric illnesses under the term Kirigai or Paithiyam, which is believed to occur due to imbalance of the three vital humors—Vali, Azhal, and Iyyam.^[2] The management of mental illnesses in the Siddha system involves a comprehensive therapeutic approach that includes internal medicines along with various external treatment modalities. Classical Siddha medical literature elaborates numerous formulations specifically indicated for psychiatric disorders. Within this framework, the Siddha text Naarpathen Siddharkal Periya Gnana Kovai describes a medicinal formulation Marunthu in the context of Pitha Karmam, indicated for ‘Payithiyangal’, a term that broadly denotes a spectrum of psychiatric conditions. This reference supports the basis for selecting the formulation.

Thus, the present narrative review aims to explore Marunthu formulation described in the context of Pitha Karmam and evaluate its potential role in the management of psychiatric disorders. This work seeks to integrate Siddha knowledge with modern scientific perspectives to develop safe, effective, and accessible therapeutic solutions for the growing burden of mental health disorders.

METHODOLOGY

This study employed a narrative literature review approach focusing on a Siddha medicinal formulation described in Naarpathen Siddharkal Periya Gnana Kovai (1st ed., Thamarai Noolagam Publication, May 1995, p. 175) within the context of Pitha Karmam. The classical details of the formulation, including its composition and traditional indications, were systematically extracted from the text. Subsequently, a literature search was conducted using the PubMed database to identify studies pertaining to the pharmacological properties of the individual ingredients.

The literature search incorporated keywords including Mental Disorders, Behavioral Symptoms, Depressive Disorder, Neuroprotection, Oxidative Stress, Zingiber officinale, Equine milk, Donkey milk, and Non-centrifugal cane sugar. These terms were applied both individually and in combination using appropriate Boolean operators to refine the search strategy. Relevant articles were screened based on titles and abstracts, and full-text articles were retrieved where necessary. Studies focusing on the pharmacological activities of the individual ingredients were included. Articles lacking relevance to the research objective were excluded. The selected studies were then critically analyzed to identify potential mechanisms of action and their relevance to psychiatric disorders, thereby facilitating the correlation between classical Siddha indications and contemporary scientific evidence.

RESULT

Classical Source and Context of *Marunthu* for *Pitha Karmam*:

The Siddha formulation *Marunthu* was identified in the text *Naarpathen Siddharkal Periya Gnana Kovai* in the context of Pitha Karma Santhi for the management of “*Payithiyangal*” (psychiatric disorders). The formulation consists of 3 ingredients. They are Inji chaaru (ginger juice) – 2 karandi, Kesari paal (donkey milk) – 4 karandi, and Karumbu vellam (sugarcane jaggery) – 2 kalanchu. The ingredients are combined and administered twice daily (iru velai) for a duration of ten days (pathu thinam), as specified in the text.

As described, the formulation is advised to be administered after performing Karma Santhi as a preparatory practice before meditation. Karma Santhi refers to a protocol comprising a set of practices intended to neutralize karmic influences prior to meditation, forming part of the therapeutic regimen before the subsequent administration of the medicine.

A similar ratio of the same ingredients is described in Pulipaani Vaithiyam 500 as an adjuvant (Anupanam) for Payithiyathirkku parpam (Peranda parpam), indicated for Pitha payithiyam and Bhramai, which correspond to clinical features of psychiatric disorders.^[3] This adjuvant is prepared by combining two parts donkey's milk with one part ginger juice, followed by the addition of an equal quantity of sugar. Peranda parpam is then triturated with this medium prior to administration. While Peranda Parpam specifies the addition of sugar (sarkkarai), the present review formulation specifies karumbu vellam (non-centrifugal cane sugar) instead, considering its potential therapeutic advantages. This overlap in both composition and therapeutic indication suggests that the formulation may have relevance in neuropsychiatric conditions. The repeated inclusion of these ingredients in classical Siddha formulations for psychiatric disorders suggests their potential therapeutic relevance.

Clinical Evidence on the Therapeutic Potential of Ginger

Evidence from multiple studies indicates that ginger (*Zingiber officinale*) and its bioactive compounds possess neuroprotective and neurobehavioral effects that may have relevance to psychiatric disorders. Experimental research has shown that treatment with phenolic-compound-rich ginger extract improved motor and cognitive impairments and reduced neuroinflammatory cytokines in the hippocampus in a mild traumatic brain injury model, demonstrating protective effects on neuronal function.^[4] In addition, a systematic review of preclinical studies reported that zingerone, a bioactive compound derived from ginger, exhibits antioxidant and anti-inflammatory properties and improves learning, memory, and behavioral outcomes in experimental models of cognitive disorders.^[5] Another review highlighted that gingerol, the principal active constituent of ginger, exerts polypharmacological neuroprotective effects, including reduction of oxidative stress, neuroinflammation, and neuronal damage, mechanisms involved in brain dysfunction.^[6]

Clinical and experimental studies further support the neuropsychiatric relevance of ginger. Supplementation with ginger extract has been reported to improve attention, working memory, and cognitive processing in healthy middle-aged women, indicating potential cognitive-enhancing effects.^[7] In addition, gingerol-enriched ginger extract has been shown to reduce anxiety-like behavior and modulate pathways related to neuroinflammation, neurotransmission, neuroplasticity, and neuroimmunity.^[8] Furthermore, the ethanolic extract of *Zingiber officinale* Roscoe exhibited significant CNS activity in mice, with the higher dose (200 mg/kg, p.o.) producing superior effects across all behavioural models. Phytochemical

screening identified phenolic compounds, flavonoids, tannins, anthocyanins, glycosides, and volatile oils as major constituents. The authors attributed the observed anxiolytic, antidepressant, and antinociceptive properties to the antioxidant potential of these phytoconstituents.^[9] Collectively, these findings suggest that ginger and its active constituents may contribute to neuroprotection, cognitive enhancement, and regulation of emotional behavior, supporting their potential relevance in the management of psychiatric and neurobehavioral disorders.

Potential Neuroprotective and Anxiolytic Effects of Donkey Milk

Research suggests that donkey milk (*Equus asinus*) contains several bioactive components that may influence neurological and mental health. A review on the health applications of donkey milk reported that its whey proteins, peptides, and other bioactive molecules contribute to various biological activities, including anti-inflammatory, antioxidant, and immunomodulatory effects, which may support overall health and physiological regulation.^[10] In addition, donkey milk has attracted scientific interest due to its nutritional composition and biological activities, including antioxidant and anti-inflammatory properties that may contribute to protection against oxidative stress and inflammatory processes in the body.^[11]

Experimental evidence further indicates a possible neurobehavioral effect of donkey milk consumption. In an animal study, repeated administration of donkey milk for 18 days reduced anxiety-like behaviors in mice and protected against oxidative damage to brain lipids, while also increasing plasma melatonin levels, a hormone involved in regulation of sleep and mood. These findings suggest that donkey milk may have potential benefits in anxiety-related disorders without producing central nervous system depressant effects.^[12] Together, these studies indicate that donkey milk possesses bioactive and neuroprotective properties that may influence brain function and emotional behavior, suggesting potential relevance for psychiatric conditions such as anxiety and other stress-related disorders, although further clinical research in humans is required.

Antioxidant and Neuroprotective Role of Non-Centrifugal Cane Sugar

Emerging evidence suggests that not all dietary sugars exert identical effects on mental health outcomes. Refined sugar, which is devoid of micronutrients and bioactive compounds, has been consistently associated with an increased risk of Depression. The findings were

consistent across different types of studies and populations, with women showing slightly higher risk than men.^[13]

In contrast, Non-centrifugal cane sugar (NCS), commonly known as sugarcane jaggery, is a traditional unrefined sweetener rich in bioactive components such as polyphenols, flavonoids, vitamins, and minerals. These compounds contribute to significant biological actions, including reduction of oxidative stress and neuroprotection, as evidenced in an in-vitro Parkinson's disease model. NCS and its derivatives are found to be non-toxic, promote mitochondrial integrity, prevent early apoptosis, and improve cellular resilience under stress. Additionally, controlled processing techniques are shown to preserve these beneficial constituents more effectively than conventional high-temperature methods, thereby enhancing its antioxidant and neuroprotective properties.^[14]

Unlike refined sugar, which is associated with adverse neuropsychiatric outcomes when consumed in excess, the inclusion of NCS in this formulations at a dose of 2 kalanchu is controlled, purposeful, and limited to a defined pharmaceutical quantity. This minimizes metabolic burden while potentially contributing antioxidant and cytoprotective effects relevant to disorders such as Depression.

Translation of Classical Units into Standardized Dosage

Traditional Siddha units describe 1 theertha karandi as approximately 1.33 mL, 1 tek karandi and 1 ney karandi as approximately 4 mL each, 1 ucchi karandi as approximately 16 mL, 1 paaladai as approximately 30 mL, and 1 ennai karandi as approximately 240 mL. The formulation includes Inji chaaru – 2 karandi, Kesari paal (donkey milk) – 4 karandi, and Karumbu vellam – 2 kalanju.^[15]

The classical text does not specify the exact type of “karandi,” leading to ambiguity in dose standardization. In contemporary literature, particularly in PubMed, there is no universally established daily dosage of donkey milk for healthy adults, as most studies focus on condition-specific therapeutic use. In one such study involving elderly individuals (aged 72–97 years), administration of 200 mL/day of donkey milk for one month demonstrated immunomodulatory benefits without adverse effects.^[16]

Based on the available evidence and considering the lack of clarity in traditional unit conversions, the classical dose of 4 karandi alavu in this context may be reasonably

approximated to ucchi karandi alavu (1 ucchi karandi = 16 mL). Accordingly, 4 ucchi karandi per dose (64 mL), administered twice daily, provides a total daily intake of 128 mL. This falls within the functional intake range reported in contemporary literature, supporting its clinical relevance. Furthermore, 1 kalanju is approximately 5.12 g, enabling better standardization of Karumbu vellam in the formulation.

Table 1: Conversion of Classical Siddha Measures into Standard Units.

Ingredient	Classical Measure	Standardized Interpretation	Approximate Quantity
Inji chaaru	2 karandi	2 Ucchi karandi	~32 mL per dose
Kesari paal	4 karandi	4 Ucchi karandi	~64 mL per dose
Karumbu vellam	2 kalanju	-	~10.24 g per dose

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the Siddha formulation Marunthu, described under Pitha Karmam, exhibits potential relevance in the management of psychiatric disorders through its neuroprotective and other therapeutic effects, as supported by the repeated use of its ingredients in classical Siddha formulations. The lack of precise definition of traditional units such as “karandi” presents a challenge for reproducibility; however, rational interpretation as ucchi karandi alavu (approximately 16 mL) provides a practical approach to dose standardization. This approximation is consistent with available clinical evidence and enhances methodological clarity and facilitates reproducibility in research settings. Therefore, While developing a standardized therapeutic formulation, the same formulation can be utilized either as an adjuvant (Anupanam) or as a standalone therapeutic agent in the management of psychiatric disorders. However, well-designed clinical trials, dose optimization studies, and long-term safety assessments are essential to substantiate efficacy and establish standardized therapeutic protocols. The integration of traditional Siddha knowledge with contemporary scientific validation may contribute to the development of evidence-based interventions in psychiatric care.

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